

Sustainable SoluTions FOR
recycling of end-of-life Hydrogen
technologies

Deliverable D7.2

Communication toolkit

Document Details

Due date	30/06/2021
Actual delivery date	30/04/2021
Lead Contractor	Environment Park
Version	First
Prepared by	Monica Risso
Input from	
Reviewed by	

Document Details

- PU - Public
- CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)

This project has received funding from the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 101007216. This Joint Undertaking receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe research.

FUEL CELLS AND HYDROGEN
JOINT UNDERTAKING

Contents

1 Executive Summary	3
2 Logo	3
3 Technical schemes	4
4 Corporate images	5
5 Flyer	6
6 Roll up	7
7 Word template	8
8 Power point template	8

List of Figures

Figure 1 Project repository	3
Figure 2 First version of the BEST4Hy project	3
Figure 3 Definitive version of BEST 4Hy logo.....	4
Figure 4 Black and white version of BEST4Hy logo	4
Figure 5 Project technical scheme	4
Figure 6 Project corporate image	5
Figure 7 Project corporate image	5
Figure 8 Project corporate image	6
Figure 9 Project flyer	6
Figure 10 Project roll up	7
Figure 11 Project Word template.....	8
Figure 12 Project Power point template.....	8

Funded by the
Fuel Cells and
Hydrogen 2 Joint
Undertaking under
grant agreement
No 101007216.

1 Executive Summary

The deliverable is developed under the frame of WP7. The goal of WP7 is disseminating project activities, exploiting properly all results obtained and guaranteeing the project outreach. The document describes the communication toolkit developed within the WP7 with some screenshots to illustrate it.

All the graphics have been designed by professionals assuring a consistent layout and visual identity among all materials (logo, technical schemes, corporate images, flyer, rollup, word and ppt template). All material is available and downloadable from the BEST4Hy internal repository.

Figure 1 Project repository

2 Logo

Figure 2 First version of the BEST4Hy project

Figure 2 above illustrates the logo developed for the proposal. It was further developed as shown in the following figures.

Funded by the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 101007216.

Figure 3 Definitive version of BEST 4Hy logo

Figure 4 Black and white version of BEST4Hy logo

3 Technical schemes

Figure 5 Project technical scheme

Funded by the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 101007216.

The scheme above was created to represent the project activities. It features on the website, where it can be used interactively to learn about each step represented.

4 Corporate images

Figure 6 Project corporate image

Figure 7 Project corporate image

Funded by the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 101007216.

Figure 8 Project corporate image

The images above represent elements of the corporate image to be used throughout the project.

5 Flyer

Figure 9 Project flyer

A flyer has been created to present the project. It contains the main details of the project, e.g. consortium, objectives, activities etc.

6 Roll up

Figure 10 Project roll up

A first version of the project roll-up has been created, as illustrated above. It is in a format ready to print should any partner require it when representing the project at an event.

Funded by the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 101007216.

7 Word template

Figure 11 Project Word template

The template represented above is to be used for the project deliverables.

8 Power point template

Figure 12 Project Power point template

The template represented above is to be used for the internal and external presentations.

Funded by the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 101007216.